

System Design Studies for the European Advanced Reusable Satellite (EARS) Architecture

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Abstract

Nowadays, a tremendous expansion of space activities is occurring. This trend provides notable benefits, but also poses serious issues regarding sustainability. Actually, a very large number of satellites equates to a lot of resources used and wasted, together with the potential for the generation of a significant amount of debris.

The EARS (European Advanced Reusable Satellite) project, funded by the European Commission in the frame of the Horizon Europe program, aims to tackle this challenge by developing a reusable small satellite platform. Moreover, since the beginning, the conceived spacecraft will allow to perform missions that need to recover the payload, like microgravity experiments, in-orbit manufacturing of special materials or substances to be then used on Earth like crystals, semiconductors, pharmaceutical items, and many others.

The logic behind the concept is to keep everything as simple as possible and, at the same time, attain the required performance and allow for modularity and flexibility. To achieve this goal, the idea foresees taking a small satellite platform and adding a recovery-propulsion module on the bottom side and an inflatable heatshield on the other upper side. The satellite will perform a controlled de-orbit thanks to a steerable propulsion system, deploy an inflatable heatshield and re-enter the atmosphere in a ballistic trajectory. The satellite will then be retrieved in mid-air by a helicopter and returned to the support facility for post-flight check. Finally, after refurbishment and re-qualification, the system can be intended for another mission cycle.

The spacecraft concept is conceived to be developed by means of a step-by-step approach, starting from a simpler, lower performing, single-use version to be later upgraded in order to improve the payload and other capabilities, together with increasing the number of mission cycles, decreasing refurbishment work and reduce time between consecutive flights.

This paper presents a summary of the system design studies performed during the first year of the project in order to define the proper architecture, identify the subsystems layout and technical solutions, and preliminary verify the feasibility of the whole concept.

Keywords: Small satellites, Deorbit, Reentry, Recovery, Reusability, Microgravity

Nomenclature

a	Major semiaxis
A	Area
b	Minor semiaxis
C_D	Drag coefficient
C_L	Lift coefficient
C_x	Opening force coefficient at infinite mass
d	distance travelled horizontally
D	Drag, Diameter
L	Lift, Length
E	Aerodynamic efficiency
F	Force
g	Gravitational acceleration
h	Altitude, distance travelled vertically
M	Spacecraft mass
X_I	opening force reduction factor

γ	the flight path angle downward
ρ	air density

Subscripts/Superscripts

B	Body
eff	Effective (for parachute or parafoil)
hs	Heatshield
op	Opening
t	Terminal
z	Vertical direction

Acronyms/Abbreviations

AAD	Automatic Activation Device
ADEPT	Adaptable, Deployable, Entry and Placement Technology
AOCS	Attitude and Orbit Control System

CEP	Circular Error Probable
CGG	Cold Gas Generator
CONOPS	Concept of Operations
EARS	European Advanced Reusable Satellite
EFESTO	European Flexible hEat Shields: advanced TPS design and tests for future in-Orbit demonstration
FTPS	Flexible Thermal Protection System
GNC	Guidance, Navigation & Control
GPS	Global Positioning System
HEART	High Energy Atmospheric Re-entry Test
CIAS	Knots Indicated Air Speed
LEC	Local Entry Corridor
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LOFTID	Low-Earth Orbit Flight Test of an Inflatable Decelerator
MAR	Mid-Air Recovery
MIFE	Mini-Irene Flight experiment
OBC	On Board Computer
ULA	United Launch Alliance

1. Introduction

After several decades of relative stagnation, the space business is now experiencing a dramatic transformation phase, which brings both great opportunities but also new issues and challenges.

The EARS project has been conceived in order to intercept several important hot topics related with the current and future situation of the Space Economy, trying at the same time to exploit the foreseen opportunities and mitigate the expected problematics.

The first topic is the boom of small satellites operating in LEO and the consequent increasing related market. However, this uncontrolled growth as the potential for the generation of a significant number of debris that can lead to a Kessler syndrome scenario, introducing the second topic, i.e. debris mitigation. Another important current subject is reusability, with the aim to reduce costs, waste of resources and pollution, in line with a general trend toward a circular economy. However, reusability is now considered mainly for launch vehicles, particularly first stages, as the re-entry from orbit poses significant higher challenges from a thermo-mechanical point of view. Finally, the last topic is the market for payloads that have to go in space but need to be later recover on Earth. Recovering the payload is necessary for in-orbit manufacturing of special components to be used on Earth. The particular conditions provided in the space environment like microgravity or radiations cannot be replicated easily on ground and thus are of special interest for the manufacturing of special materials or substances, like crystals, semiconductors or pharmaceutical items. The same applies for scientific experiments, adding also the possibility to take

measurements on the lower layers of the upper atmosphere during re-entry. Recent activities and developments seem to confirm the increasing interest toward the payload recovery market [1-4].

The idea behind the EARS (European Advanced Reusable Satellite) project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe's research and innovation programme, is to develop a spacecraft with an innovative architecture that is able to answer to all the opportunities and issues just presented. In particular, the final vision of EARS is to develop a reusable satellite that can be sent and operated in space, deorbited, recovered and reused again. For a general description of the EARS program the reader is referred to [5,6].

The EARS concept is designed to maintain simplicity while delivering the necessary performance, along with modularity and flexibility. To accomplish this, a small satellite platform is equipped with a recovery-propulsion module on its lower side and an inflatable heatshield on the upper side (see Fig. 1). Using a steerable propulsion system, the satellite performs a controlled de-orbit, deploying the heatshield and re-entering the atmosphere along a ballistic trajectory. Once in the atmosphere, the satellite is retrieved mid-air by a helicopter and returned to the support facility for post-flight inspections (see Fig. 2). After refurbishment and re-qualification, the system can be reused for another mission cycle.

Fig. 1. EARS Conceptual layout

- EARS CONOPS
1. De-orbit burn
 2. Flip maneuver
 3. Heatshield inflation/deployment
 4. Passive Entry
 5. Decelerator Deployment (Parafoil)
 6. Helicopter MAR

Fig. 2. EARS CONOPS

The spacecraft concept is planned to follow a step-by-step development approach, starting with a basic, lower-performance single-use model. This version will be gradually upgraded over time to improve payload capacity and other capabilities, while also increasing the number of mission cycles, minimizing refurbishment efforts, and reducing the turnaround time between flights.

The proposed concept differs significantly from typical re-entry solutions like spaceplanes and capsules that cover niche applications because the EARS goal is to maintain the spacecraft as similar as possible to a conventional satellite in order to keep commonalities in design, components, capabilities operations and market.

For an extensive discussion on the EARS design philosophy and approach the reader is referred to [7].

The EARS Consortium is led by the “Nello Carrara” Institute of Applied Physics from the Italian Research Council (CNR – IFAC), with five other partners: University of Padua (UNIPD), Deimos (DES), Von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics (VKI), Technology for Propulsion and Innovation (T4i), and Kongsberg NanoAvionics (KNA). The University of Padua is responsible of the system level studies, Deimos of the mission and heatshield design together with the GNC development, VKI of the heatshield material selection and test, T4i of the propulsion and KNA of the platform.

The next chapters will describe the preliminary design of the main subsystems composing the EARS spacecraft, starting with the platform, followed by the heatshield, then the recovery section and finally the propulsion system. Some other aspects and concluding remarks will be discussed in chapter 6.

2. Platform

The starting point for the EARS spacecraft is the selection of an existing bus to form the basis for the reusable satellite. Two state-of-the-art space proven small satellite platforms from KNA belonging to different categories have been taken into initial consideration: the 16U CubeSat M16P [8] and the larger MP42 [9]. The latter is a modular bus that can accommodate a payload with an area around 480x490 mm with a total maximum satellite length and mass of 1.3m and 150 kg, respectively.

The CubeSat has been discarded for several reasons, first of all because the small size hindered the possibility to achieve recovery with a meaningful payload without massive technical breakthroughs. Moreover, the performance and flexibility of the CubeSat were deemed less attractive for the foreseen market of payloads that require post-mission recovery. The elongated shape of the M16P is also more problematic for aerodynamic stability during re-entry. Finally, CubeSats are launched in orbit inside a box

[10]. Once a panel opens, the springs on the bottom eject the satellite. This storage configuration limits the possibility to modify the shape of the standard CubeSat.

Instead, the MP42 (Fig. 3) bus is bigger, more flexible, way more capable, with a boxier shape, which helps in the design of the heatshield and with the aerodynamic stability at re-entry. It is also more expensive, but it is cheaper in terms of cost per kg and cost vs performance. The satellite is launched into orbit exposed and connected on the launch vehicle with a detachment ring on the bottom [11], which allows to add protrusion to the spacecraft external shape, again helping with the heatshield design. Its size is a perfect compromise between being not too small for the proposed task like a CubeSat but also not too large in order to keep the typical advantages of small satellites like modularity, flexibility, lower costs and shorter lead times, possibility of multiple launch opportunities, potential for mass production.

Fig. 3. KNA MP42 satellite bus [9]

Excluding the specific subsystems added for re-entry and recovery described in the following chapters, the MP42 bus has already most of the necessary components (e.g. solar panels, batteries, power management, OBC, AOCS, sensors, communication and so on) and required capabilities. The main modifications to be expected are related with the connection (physical, electrical and software) of the propulsion/recovery and heatshield modules and the need to survive multiple cycles of launch to and recovery from space. These aspects are discussed in more detail in chapter 6.

3. Heatshield

3.1 Heatshield overview

The heatshield has the fundamental function to protect the satellite during re-entry. A basic requirement of the EARS project in order to keep the maximum flexibility and functionality of the satellite in orbit is the use of a heatshield than can be enclosed in a small

volume and opened only just before re-entry. To do so, the available options are the inflatable or deployable heatshield. After a careful comparison (Table 1), the inflatable heatshield solution has been determined as the most promising for the EARS architecture, particularly for its flexibility. In fact, the most promising feature of the inflatable heatshield is the possibility to be stored in a small box and let the spacecraft operate in orbit like a conventional one. On the contrary, the deployable system tends always to enclose around the satellite limiting its capabilities unless a very complex internally foldable design is considered.

Table 1. Inflatable and deployable heatshields comparison

Inflatable	Deployable
Used mainly for heavy satellites	Extensive study for smaller satellite
Successfully tested in orbit (LOFTID [12])	Sub-orbital tests (ADEPT [13], MIFE [14])
More public information regarding the mass budget for the heat shield	Limitations on the public information regarding the mass budget
Worse packing density values	No definite data available, nevertheless it is expected to provide slightly favourable packing density values
Large volume usage	The deployable arms normally don't take volume, when located in the satellite faces, but need thermal protection. This can also lead to a drift from the conventional U shape factor.
Easier to adapt to non-cylindrical structures	Need for a structure to adapt/interface the rectangular/cubic shape to a circular one
Easier stowing, easier integration with the solar panels	More difficult to stow the FTPS cloth, less likely the integration with solar panels
Modular design	Requires integral design with the structure

The re-entry trajectory has been then determined in the mission analysis (Fig. 4). The following constraints have been imposed in order to guarantee the feasibility of the required technologies:

- Dynamic Pressure: 12 kPa
- Heat Load: 60 MJ/m²

- Heat Flux: 600 kW/m²
- Load factor: 12 g
- Landing accuracy: 150 km

These constraints have been selected in order to be compliant with currently available state-of-the-art technology and not require breakthrough (i.e. expensive and risky) developments. For further details, the reader is referred to [15].

Fig. 4. Reference trajectory velocity altitude envelope during re-entry

Afterwards, heat flux and pressure evolutions have been calculated (Fig. 5 and 6, respectively) together with mechanical and heat loads (Fig. 7 and 8, respectively). The heatshield diameter has been defined as 1.87 m, allowing a relatively low ballistic coefficient of 28 kg/m³ and a slow descent. The initial flight path angle is -1.65°. The required ΔV is 100 m/s. In order to cope with the specified drop zone dispersion, the pointing accuracy of the thrust should be better than $\pm 1^\circ$ (3σ) and the ΔV error should be less than 2.5% (3σ).

Fig. 5. Reference total heat flux evolution during re-entry

Fig. 6. Reference dynamic pressure evolution during re-entry

Fig. 7. Reference loads evolution during re-entry, acceleration

Fig. 8. Reference loads evolution during re-entry, heat

3.2 Heatshield preliminary sizing

The heat shield mass was calculated by performing a volumetric scaling of the system mass, taking as reference other inflatable heat shield missions, LOFTID,

HEART [16] and EFESTO [17]. EFESTO is the mission with the smaller diameter, and therefore, the values obtained with the scaling will be more reliable. The results of this scaling are shown in Table 2, and the current mass estimation for the heat shield is of almost 13 kg. The inflatable structure and FTPS need to be stowed in the satellite. To calculate the volume required to stow the fabrics, a conservative value of 200 kg/m³ for the packing density has been used.

Table 2. EARS heatshield preliminary mass estimation

Component	Mass estimation (kg)
Inflatable Structure + FTPS	8.32
Rigid nose (RTPS)	3.54
Inflation System (CGG)	0.8
Heatshield mass estimation	12.66

To size the inflation system, a tension cone configuration was assumed for the heatshield. Knowing the gas volume and the inflation pressure, required gas mass to fill the inflatable structure can be obtained straightforwardly. Assuming that the gas used is N₂, the mass required is around 70 g. Looking at cold gas generators specification sheets it is seen that to generate this mass of N₂, two CGG are required, weighting 400 g each.

The heat shield is composed by a fixed part and an inflatable part. The inflatable part is enclosed during mission until re-entry. The fixed part is a cone that protrudes laterally from the spacecraft as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Heatshield nose cap configuration

Figure 10, on the other hand sketches the deployed configuration of the aeroshape. The black section refers to the rigid heatshield spherical nose section, which is connected to the yellow conical part, of the heatshield,

which is clothed with Flexible Thermal Protection System (FTPS).

Fig. 10. Heatshield preliminary sizing

Table 3 summarizes the design parameters for the aeroshape and the heatshield bay.

Table 3. Aeroshape design parameters

Parameter	Dimension	Unit
Deployed Diameter	1.878	m
Nose Radius	0.707	m
Cone Angle	60	degrees
Stowed FTPS bay	0.16x0.5x0.5	m

The parameters reported in Table 3 are a direct follow up of the analysis carried out and reported in [15], in particular, the diameter constraint is limited on one side by the (highest) feasible ballistic coefficient, and on the other hand by the constraint to minimize the expected FTPS fabric needs. The bigger the nose radius, the lower the peak heat fluxes, on the other hand there are limitations on the maximum surface allocation for the rigid heatshield spherical section (interface with the rest of the MP42 platform). Literature review, for Earth applications show little variability as far as cone angles is concerned. The usual values range between 45° and 60°, being 45° the most stable (and less efficient, from a mass standpoint), and 60° a good compromise in terms of stability and mass efficiency. Due to the initial conditions and consequently due to the de-orbiting conditions, the nose radius is a limiting constraint: LEC is closed by heat flux constraint. Therefore, the cone angle choice of 60° is also maximizing the nose radius, as the maximum dimension of the rigid heatshield is limited by the platform base area.

Regarding the materials used for the heatshield, as already explained the heat shield is made of two main parts: a rigid, fixed nose and a flexible thermal protection system (FTPS). The former must withstand the peak thermal loads and will be manufactured from high performing composite ceramics. The latter is a multilayer structure made by an outer layer which interacts with the external environment and is exposed to the highest temperature and an inner one which prevents the diffusion of heat and insulates the internal structures of the system.

A preliminary trade-off is done considering different material candidates for both the rigid nose and the outer layer and the inner layer of the FTPS and it is based on availability of the material, its performances, costs, and its provenience. VKI is responsible to identify and tests the proper materials for all the heatshield items [18].

4. Recovery

4.1 Recovery overview

As anticipated in the introduction one of the specific subsystems of the EARS platform is the recovery system. Following the underlying philosophy of simplicity, the EARS platform is foreseen to re-enter the atmosphere passively in a ballistic trajectory. Compared to other competitors, the commanded deorbit burn allows the re-entry to be located in a specific place and time, facilitating the placement of the ground segment and the overall operations. However, compared to a fully controlled solution, such a passive final re-entry will introduce a certain amount of geographical dispersion. The idea of EARS is to compensate for this uncertainty both with the flight of the helicopter and with a controlled descent under a guided parafoil. Moreover, mid-air retrieval of the payload allows also for both re-entry over land and over sea without the need for special protections toward impact or seawater.

Mid-Air Recovery (MAR) has been developed for many different purposes over the last 50 years [19], including the retrieval of unmanned air vehicles and air-launched cruise missiles. The first-generation of MAR utilized multiple engagement hooks attached to poles below aircraft. The hooks were connected to a special constant-tension winch that decreased loads and oscillation between the helicopter and payload by paying out line at a pre-set tension, generally about 1.25 times the weight of the payload. The payload floated beneath a round parachute, which, due to the round parachute's static nature, had to be hit accurately just as the aircraft flew through the wake of the parachute.

Second-generation MAR upgraded to the use of a parafoil system that allowed the intercepting aircraft to fly in formation with the payload. Parafoils are designed to fly along a relatively straight path, facilitating a more

controlled and smoother retrieval than round parachutes that hover in an unstable downward float.

Third-generation MAR improves on second generation MAR with the addition of a trailing suspension line connected directly to the supported payload. This allows much heavier loads to be captured, limited by the helicopter performance. In 2005 the Atlas program partnered with Vertigo, Inc to demonstrate third level MAR, capturing a ~200 lb person [20]. In 2007, ULA and Vertigo partnered to conduct two tests: the MAR of a 750-lb pod, demonstrating higher capture mass and transition load, and the MAR of a skydiver with an improved remote-controlled grapple hook.

Third-generation MAR has several advantages that makes it perfect for the EARS project:

- Commercial context
- Commercially available aircraft
- No aircraft modifications or “experimental” classification required
- Low-speed, low-g pick-up:
 - Easy on Helicopter and payload; **0.2g demonstrated**
 - Matched speed for precise pick-up
- Limited training required

The reliability of the first MAR systems (1960s 1970s) was 75%-88% and it is approaching 100% today.

Fig. 11. Third generation MAR of a skydiver [20]

The capture of skydivers and passive pods (Fig. 11) is very important as shows the complete feasibility of the EARS design. In fact, the size (nominally 0.5x0.5x1.1 m) and mass (nominally 120 kg) of the proposed spacecraft are compatible with those of a skydiver, enabling the use of commercial components with large availability, low cost, high reliability and long heritage. Moreover, it is easy to find data on standard parachutes behavior. A typical skydiver experiences a deceleration from 54 m/s to 2.7 m/s in the 2 seconds needed for the parachute to fully inflate. This

corresponds to a negative acceleration of less than **3g**, well below the design load of the original platform.

In the case of EARS, terminal velocity will be determined by the system ballistic coefficient, which depends on the 120 kg total mass divided by the product of the inflatable heatshield drag coefficient and area. At equilibrium the drag equals the weight of the system:

$$Mg = 0.5\rho v_t^2 C_{Dhs} A_{hs} \quad (1)$$

Considering a drag coefficient equal to 0.8 and a diameter of the heatshield of 1.87 m for an area of 2.74 m², taking the air density at 10 km (0.41 kg/m³) one obtains a terminal velocity of 52 m/s (below 200 km/h), which is compatible with a conventional skydiver. The altitude of 10 km has been selected as a trade-off because it is necessary to slow down the spacecraft to a reasonable low velocity and open the parachute at an altitude that is well proven for commercial systems and that can be tested easily. Moreover, the platform should not spend too much time in unconventional layers of the atmosphere. At the same time, however, the highest is the altitude the longest is the descent time, allowing the helicopter and the parafoil to travel longer distances, better compensating for the initial dispersion.

When the parachute opens it is possible to calculate the opening force:

$$F = 0.5\rho v_{op}^2 C_D A_{eff} C_x X_1 \quad (2)$$

The opening force reduction factor X_1 takes into account the fact that for low loadings the mass starts to decelerate before full inflation [21] (see Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. Opening Force Reduction Factor vs. Canopy Loading [21]

Dividing the force for the mass is it possible to calculate the system deceleration, again a value slightly below 3g is obtained. The maximum deceleration is also controlled thanks to a slider that has a reefing effect on parachute deployment.

Moreover, shock absorbers can be used to limit the maximum load on the system. They are used to damp the shock loads generated from the inflation of the parachute. A possible design consists of a cord folded on itself and stitched. The load is damped by breaking the seams.

The parachute system is composed of a drogue parachute and the main parachute. The smaller drogue parachute is easier to deploy and is used to pull off with its own drag the main parachute or parafoil, which instead has the function to fly the payload during the rest of the descent.

The parachute line is connected to the platform by a 3-rings riser used in all the skydiving equipment. The riser is used as a release system to set free the parachute: once the cutter breaks the loop cord, the rings are free to move. In this way, it is possible to control the parachute actuation by the simple cutting of the loop cord. Afterwards the drag that acts on the drogue chute can pull out the main parachute. Using this solution, the load acts on the bigger ring and on the webbing which strength is far greater than the one of the loop cord. An example of a 3-rings release system is provided by Mirage [22]. The fact that the loop cord does not have to carry the full loads means it can be broken with a small cutter. A widely used cutter in the skydiving industry is provided by CYPRES [23]. It has a cutting force of 2 kN. It is used to open the 3-rings release system and consequently eject the parachute. Each release system is composed of 2 independent cutters for redundancy.

It has been decided to put the recovery bay on the back of the spacecraft. There are multiple reasons for this choice. The backward placement allows to place the recovery bay in the same module that contains the propulsion system, outside the baseline KNA platform, in order to avoid modification to the standard equipment and follow the philosophy of modularity. As it will be shown later, the peculiar position of the thrusters leaves a free space to be used effectively by the recovery bay. Moreover, the parachute is placed on the opposite side respect with the heatshield to avoid interference and facilitate deployment. The parachute is also deployed backward. This solution put the parachute in the wake of the satellite. For vertical descending bodies the distance L_T between the vehicle rear edge and canopy leading edge should be equivalent $6 D_B$ [21] (Fig. 13) to avoid the blanketing or wake effect of the vehicle body.

Ejecting the parachute sideways can provide good inflation with shorter distances. However, this option has been discarded for several reasons. One is that it was more difficult to implement due to the geometry and placement of the thrusters. Moreover, it is easier to define the load direction and behavior for an axial deployment. Finally, with side ejection there are more risks related to the unknown rotational position of the satellite at the moment of parachute release. This could

create problems, for example, during oscillations, if the ejecting side is looking toward the ground. For this reason, side ejection is often performed with mortars that provide more distance to the parachute from the platform. This adds further complexity that it was decided to avoid.

Fig. 13. Canopy Distance to Minimize the Forebody Wake [21]

In the case of a parafoil the air is coming mainly horizontally during steady flight, but the problem still needs to be considered during the deployment phase.

One remaining critical issue is related to the fact that the heatshield produces a much larger wake than the satellite body (which, of course, is exactly the motivation for its use during re-entry). For this reason, the conceived parachute deployment technique could probably not be implemented without considering a mitigation to the heatshield wake issue. This aspect will be further discussed in the next subsection.

The mass of the parachute is proportional to its size. Total mass is much higher than the parachute surface multiplied by its density to account for all auxiliary items but remains roughly proportional to the parachute size. A parachute system designed for skydiving includes a container/harness, a main canopy, a reserve one, and an Automatic Activation Device (AAD). The whole thing weighs around 9-11 kg for a student parachute, and, as the size of the canopy needed for landing safely decreases with experience, it can go down to around 7 kg. On the other hand, a tandem parachute needs a bigger canopy and stronger gear and weighs around 14 kg. A brand-new parachute system like these ones usually costs between 7000 (single) and 14000 (tandem) \$. A parachute system designed for emergency situations, such the ones designed for aircraft pilots, only contains a single emergency canopy in the container, and they usually weigh between 7 and 9 kg (this kind of system usually costs between 1000 and 3000 \$). BASE jumping parachutes can fit into this category, even if their design is quite specific.

4.2 Recovery sizing

The descent rate for a classical parachute is determined by its drag:

$$Mg = 0.5\rho v_z^2 C_D A_{eff} \quad (3)$$

The descent rate v_z decreases during the descent because the atmospheric density increases. In the case of a flight under parafoil the system is gliding and the weight is mainly compensated by the lift:

$$Mg = 0.5\rho v^2 C_L A_{eff} \cos\gamma + 0.5\rho v^2 C_D A_{eff} \sin\gamma$$

$$v_z = v \sin\gamma$$

$$\tan\gamma = D/L = 1/E = h/d \quad (4)$$

Again, the descent rate v_z decreases during the descent due to the thicker atmosphere. As the equations for the parafoil show, it is important to have a high efficiency in order to travel a significant distance for the same loss of altitude. Moreover, the descent rate is much smaller than the flight velocity. Even if the lift coefficient of the parafoil is lower than the drag coefficient of the parachute, the fact that the parafoil can fly at a much higher speed than its descent rate, considering that the effect of speed is squared, allows the parafoil to require a lower surface area.

A parachute of 9 m in diameter, with an area of 64 m², a drag coefficient of 2.2 and a carried load of 120 kg will descent from 10 to 1 km at an average speed of 5 m/s (Fig. 14 and 15).

On the other hand, a parafoil carrying the same payload of 120 kg will descent from 10 to 1 km at an average speed of 5 m/s with an area of only 15 m² (Fig. 16 and 17).

The wing loading of the parafoil is on the order of 8 kg/m², i.e. 1.64 lbs/ft², which is considered compatible with an advanced skydiver (600-1500 jumps). Expert skydivers (>1500 jumps) can reach up to 4 lbs/ft².

Fig. 14. 64 m² parachute descent profile

Fig. 15. 64 m² parachute descent rate

Fig. 16. 15 m² parafoil descent profile

Fig. 17. 15 m² parafoil descent rate

Typically, a tandem chute used with beginners has a surface area of 350 to 500 square feet (32-46 m²) for a much more relaxed wing loading below 1 lb/ft². On the

opposite, a parafoil for a single expert skydiver will be much smaller.

As a comparison, a typical military parachute with a parabolic shape like the T10-C has a mass of 14 kg, a diameter of 10.7 m for an area of 90 m². It can be opened up to a maximum speed of 278 km/h and can decelerate a weight up to 163 kg up to 4.8-5.8 m/s. The advantage of the conventional parachute is that it does not need to be controlled and the landing speed is exactly equal to the descent rate. The parafoil needs more control and its flight speed is much higher than the descent rate, so a specific maneuver is needed for landing. However, in the case of EARS the landing is avoided, and the horizontal flight speed is instead a benefit that makes the operations simpler for the helicopter. Moreover, the controllability allows to partially compensate for wind and re-entry dispersions.

Autonomous GPS guided precision airdrop systems have been already developed, particularly for military applications. One example is the Onyx family from Atair Aerospace [24,25]. It is available in different payload configurations from 20 lbs to 2200 lbs. In particular, the Onyx ML (Micro-Light) is in the same order of magnitude as EARS, with a payload up to 150 lbs (68 kg) and Canopy sizes of 50 ft² or 120 ft² (5 m² or 11 m²). It is a lightweight, rugged and compact system that is one-person recoverable.

Some key features of the Onyx Systems that are relevant for EARS are listed in the following [24,25]:

- Accuracy: Better than 50 m CEP
- High glide ratio over 4.5:1 provides a horizontal standoff of 44 km from an altitude of 35,000 ft (11 km)
- Deployable from military fixed-wing and rotary aircraft up to 150 KIAS (278 km/h)
- Continuously dis-reefed guidance parafoil provides for lowest opening shock and high-speed deployment capabilities
- Fully recoverable, modular, and reusable system
- Very “rigger-friendly”, designed by former U.S. Marine Corps military riggers. Onyx ML parachutes are packed identically as personnel parachutes
- Rigging time: packed, rigged, and programmed by one military rigger in less than 30 minutes.

For the parafoil a lift coefficient of 0.7 and a drag coefficient of 0.16 have been considered [26]. Thus, the parafoil efficiency is 4.375. The transversal drag of the satellite has been calculated for an area of 0.5x1.1 = 0.55 m² and a drag coefficient of 1. The final drag coefficient of the system is consequently 0.2 for the reference area of 15 m². The efficiency of the complete system drops to 3.5. In a descent from 10 to 1 km such a

system will travel more than 30 km in roughly 30 minutes. The angle of descent is around 16°.

In these calculations the heatshield has not been included. The heatshield has a large area that can produce a relevant drag also in the tangential direction, reducing the gliding efficiency. Moreover, it can partially destabilize the gliding. Finally, as anticipated before, it can hinder parafoil deployment. It is therefore necessary to reduce its impact in the final part of the atmospheric flight.

One possibility is to drop the heatshield. This could be a possible option, particularly at the beginning of the development because the heatshield is the part that sustains the highest thermal loads during re-entry and consequently is difficult to reuse, even if the preliminary work performed by VKI seems promising in this regard [18]. The biggest advantage is the weight saving and aerodynamic benefits during parafoil gliding. Drawbacks of this solution are, first of all, the impossibility of reuse (unless it is caught on ground or floating on water), then the complexity of the ejection and related parts, and finally the potential safety and pollution aspects of dropping the heatshield from altitude. The ejection is easier after parachute deployment but does not solve the parachute extraction interference, on the other hand if done in advance it becomes more difficult as the upper satellite has a much higher ballistic coefficient than the lower heatshield making the ejection troublesome.

Another alternative and perhaps the most attractive solution is to add a relief valve that can deflate the heatshield prior to parafoil extraction (Fig. 18). This option is conceptually simpler, more reliable and allows for full recovery, however it needs further investigation regarding the final shape that the deflated heatshield would have and its aerodynamic behavior.

Fig. 18. Possible heatshield management during parafoil gliding

The predicted recovery system mass is between 10 and 15 kg with a volume of 17 liters. The recovery bay is a cylinder of 300 mm in diameter for 250 mm of length placed in the same module that contains the

propulsion system. The idea is to use a simple shape in order to favor the deployment of the system while minimizing issues. Due to the position of the thrusters and the circular deployment ring it was decided to put the recovery bay in an internal cylinder as the only reasonable option.

The sizing of the EARS recovery bay has been also compared with the one used on a sounding rocket flown by T4i in February 2022 [27,28]. Actual data are classified but the empty mass of the rocket was very similar to the EARS one and the mass/volume of the recovery bay were compared accordingly.

Fig. 19. Rear view of the recovery bay (red) in the bottom module (translucent, deployment ring in black)

Regarding the helicopter mid-air retrieval, several aerial platforms are available at a reasonable cost with higher than necessary performance. A typical example of a well-known and widespread modern helicopter is the AgustaWestland (now Leonardo) AW139. It can fly at speeds up to 300 km/h, it can stay in flight for hours and travel for several hundreds of km. This margin is not only important for the final satellite chasing but also for the transfer and waiting phases into the operative zone before and after the catching maneuver. The cost per hour is around 1250 \$, which makes a reasonable expense compared with actual space activities costs.

As previously mentioned, the satellite can glide under the parafoil for 30 km during a period of 30 minutes. At a reasonable speed of 250 km/h, the helicopter can travel for another 125 km, for a total of more than 150 km. This is also roughly the maximum distance expected if the helicopter is placed on the side of the drop zones (Fig. 20). In fact, the semi-major axis a of the dispersion ellipse (3σ) is estimated around 150 km while the semi-minor axis b should be on the order

of 20 km. The semi-major axis will be pointing in the re-entry direction. Fig. 22 shows the calculation of the actual distance travelled by the helicopter towards the opposite boundary of the drop zone. As expected, the distance is $2b$ when the spacecraft falls exactly on the opposite side of the ellipse. The distance increases as the drop point moves toward the longitudinal end of the ellipse. Because of the elongated shape of the ellipse the maximum distance is located near this point, and it is almost equal to the hypotenuse formed by a and b , which in turn for the same reason is only slightly higher than a , i.e. 150 km.

Fig. 20. Drop zone with one helicopter

Fig. 21. Distance travelled by one helicopter towards the boundary of the drop zone

Due to the relatively low cost of the helicopter platform, in case more margin is required, two units can be used, halving the required distance to be travelled (see Fig. 22). At the moment of the mid-air retrieval, the EARS satellite is gliding around 14.5 m/s (52 km/h) with 4 m/s of vertical speed (Fig. 17).

Fig. 22. Drop zone with two helicopters

Further details on the GNC solution for the parafoil-based recovery of the EARS reusable satellite can be found in [29].

5. Propulsion

5.1 Propulsion system overview

As anticipated in the introduction, the EARS propulsion system is used for the controlled deorbit of the spacecraft and is placed on the bottom module. It is composed by four identical chemical propulsion units that together provide the capability of thrust steering.

Chemical propulsion has been selected for several reasons. First of all, the need of propulsion is related to the fact that ERAS has to re-enter in a specific place at a specific time, and uncontrolled re-entry is not an option. Compared to other solutions like drag sails, tethers, electrical propulsion and so on, chemical propulsion is a highly mature technology that can work very fast in any condition, providing a unique capability. Reliable and consistent high thrust is fundamental for precise and simple re-entry. Moreover, chemical propulsion can be used at any altitude for any kind of orbital manoeuvre. The only drawback is a potentially higher weight compared to some other solutions, but this should be limited considering the ΔV involved and it is definitely compensated by all the other advantages and lack of issues compared with the alternatives.

From the mission analysis a 100 m/s ΔV was determined as necessary for de-orbit. It was decided to size the system for **200 m/s** in order to have more margin and also to allow the platform to have some motion capability in orbit. As a rule of thumb, 100 m/s allow to change the altitude by little less than 200 km.

Based on the mission analysis, a **40 N** thrust was deemed viable for the propulsion system. Higher thrusts would imply more difficulties with acceleration loads, GNC and propulsion system weight. Lower thrusts

could increase too much the duration of the burning time, affecting the precision of the ballistic unguided re-entry. Considering 120 kg of mass of the full platform, 200 m/s correspond to a total impulse of **240 kNs**. For 40 N of nominal thrust this translates in **600 s** of nominal firing time. The burning time for the de-orbit manoeuvre (100 m/s) will be on the order of 300 s. This represents less than 6% of a typical LEO revolution period, which is on the order of 90-100 minutes, justifying the hypothesis of impulsive behaviour.

Regarding the type of chemical thrusters, liquids are the only option that can operate for such long burning times at low thrusts [30,31]. Moreover, liquids are more suited to be designed for reusability. The required ΔV is high enough (with the limited mass budget) to necessitate the use of a bipropellant propulsion system. A monopropellant system will be simpler but will require more mass and size because of the lower specific impulse.

Considering the propellants, the choice has been restricted to largely available green chemicals coherently with the current trend of economic and environmental sustainability.

Hydrogen peroxide has been selected as oxidizer from the green ones for its room temperature storability, high density (around 1390 kg/m³), high performance and low vapor pressure. On the opposite the other main green oxidizer, nitrous oxide, has a much lower density and a very high vapor pressure particularly above 30°C (critical point at 36°C, 72 bar, 452 kg/m³), requiring larger, thicker tanks and higher pressure ratings for all fluidic components. Moreover, nitrous oxide properties vary significantly in proximity of the critical point.

Hydrogen peroxide can be easily decomposed through a catalyst to produce hot oxygen and steam. This has two benefits. Firstly, hydrogen peroxide can be used in both monopropellant and bi-propellant mode on the same engine, giving the possibility to have two levels of thrust by simply opening and closing the fuel valve, with a throttling ratio approximately equal to **2:1**. The second benefit is related to the possibility to vaporize and ignite the propellants without a specific external item, simplifying the architecture, increasing reliability, guaranteeing multiple starts and stops and keeping the combustion stable and efficient in a relatively simple way, exploiting on a staged combustion after monopropellant decomposition architecture.

Regarding the fuel, propane was selected for the following reasons. Propane is a widely available green fuel, cheap and easy to procure. In terms of specific impulse and safety it is in line with other hydrocarbon fuels. However, it has a moderate vapor pressure that is lower than nitrous oxide, guaranteeing lighter tanks but it is still high enough at room temperature to provide the capability for self-pressurization. In this way the system is pressurized by the fuel itself, significantly simplifying

the architecture of the propulsion system. The idea is to use this capability also to pressurize the hydrogen peroxide using a separation interface, both for the necessary safety reason and for microgravity propellant management. Temperature sensitivity is still an issue for all self-pressurized fluids but is less dramatic than with nitrous oxide as the critical point is now more far away (96°C, 42.5 bar) from the operational one (Fig. 23).

Fig. 23. Propane saturation curve

As the pressurization of the propulsion system is provided by the propane vapor pressure, the initial pressure is dependent on the initial temperature as shown in Fig. 23. Moreover, during the discharge, the pressure decrease as energy is used to vaporize part of the fuel to fill the increasing ullage volume. For the simulation of the self-pressurized discharge process of the propulsion system the reader is referred to [32].

It is worth noting that hydrogen peroxide and propane operate with a relatively high oxidizer to fuel ratio of around 7 (Fig. 24), thus most of the propellant is the high density and monopropellant operable hydrogen peroxide.

Fig. 24. Hydrogen peroxide - propane theoretical specific impulse vs mixture ratio (O/F) [32]

Another reason for choosing saturated propane instead of some pure liquid alternatives like kerosene or ethanol is the possibility to extract the vapor phase or to easily vaporize it when drained in the liquid phase. Extract the fluid in vapor phase can be useful for cold gas thrusters used in a reaction control system. On the other hand, vaporizing the fuel is also very important for small bipropellant engines because of the size of the injecting holes, which becomes very challenging for high density liquid fuels, which consequently would suffer from poor atomization. Moreover, small engines have inherently short residence times, so it is really helpful to skip the atomization and vaporization steps in the combustion chamber. Vaporization of the small mass flow of fuel can be done by properly flowing it near some hot parts of the engine. As the fuel is saturated, vaporization is simpler than with liquids like kerosene, ethanol and the like. Cooking issues are also mitigated with propane.

Other than the higher complexity of the fluidic, tanks and thrusters, bipropellant systems have one major complication compared to monopropellant ones: the thermal environment. Bipropellant thrust chambers must deal with combustion temperatures way higher than 2000°C. In this regard hydrogen peroxide has also the advantage compared to nitrous oxide of having lower combustion temperatures. Anyway, temperatures are still too high to be sustained by simple materials. Ablative cooling is difficult to apply for small thrusts and long burning times and is inherently not reusable. Regenerative cooling is very difficult to apply at very small scales because the channels tend to become too small and the thermal gradients too steep [33,34]. The strategy foreseen for EARS is to use a combination of commercial modern high temperature resistant materials (eventually 3D printed) in critical regions and to self-protect the chamber walls as much as possible by the internal fluid dynamic design [35]. Again, the catalyst decomposition can help to create a moderate temperature gaseous flow to be used also for internal cooling.

5.2 Propulsion system architecture

Regarding the propulsion architecture, first of all two configurations were compared: one with a single engine at the centre of the back side of the satellite and the other with 4 thrusters of 10 N. The aim of the EARS project is to design a system that can perform the foreseen mission, but at the same time to exploit the technologies developed for a broader range of applications. In this regard, it is important to highlight that the 10 N thrusters are supposed to have a higher commercial market potential than the 40 N one. The 40 N thruster on the other end has the potential to be more efficient from a performance point of view, as liquid engines tend to improve asymptotically with scale,

particularly at small thrust levels. Moreover 4 engines will have 4 times the number of valves of a single engine, which is less favourable. Both engines can have difficulties in managing the thermal radiation from the hot parts. In the case of the 4 engines, however, if their placement is on the outer perimeter of the satellite base the thermal management issue can be simplified significantly as the thruster could have a complete side exposed to space (Fig. 25). Moreover, this arrangement simplifies the placement of a cylindrical recovery bay at the centre of the bottom module (again Fig. 25).

Fig. 25. External view of the propulsion-recovery module at the bottom of the spacecraft.

Both configurations require multiple tanks because the space available on the bottom of the satellite is more spread on the horizontal plane (0.5x0.5 m) than in the vertical one (0.25 m), so only several smaller tanks can be inserted effectively, unless complex shapes like toroidal tanks are used. However, keeping in mind the EARS philosophy based on simplicity, modularity and commercial value of the developed items, this kind of exotic solutions have been discarded. The multiple thrusters have the advantage to potentially perform attitude control on two axes during firing using differential thrust.

Both configurations will produce torques due to misalignment of the thrusters or the centre of mass. For this reasons all the possible torques have been calculated in order to assess the feasibility of the attitude control during firing. An uncertainty of 10 mm in the centre of mass of the satellite has been considered.

In the case of a single thruster, the attitude control can be performed only by the external systems like reaction wheels such as the ones already available from KNA catalogue. The calculations show that the torque produced can be compensated by those systems, but the momentum integral is too high. Consequently, the only alternatives are the use of a gimballed thruster, which is

a complex solution, or to use a cold gas system based on propane. In this case the cold gas thrusters are placed on the external perimeter in order to have the maximum arm and produce as much torque with the lowest possible thrust, i.e. propellant consumption. As the only objective of the deorbit firing is to produce an axial thrust, this propellant consumption is a penalty that should be kept to a minimum. This has been taken into account defining an **equivalent specific impulse**, i.e. the specific impulse calculated with the axial total impulse but referred to the whole propellant mass consumption including the attitude control. The ratio between the liquid engine specific impulse and this equivalent specific impulse determines the propellant penalty (and the inverse is the performance loss).

Regarding the four engines, the cold gas thrusters have to provide only roll control during firing. For the attitude control on the yaw and pitch axes, the function is performed by throttling differentially the four thrusters. Placing the four engines at the outer perimeter of the satellite base increases their arm and thus the torque output produced (Fig. 25).

At such small scales valves are usually on-off [36], consequently differential steering is obtained by closing the fuel valve and shifting from bipropellant to monopropellant operation. This guarantee two levels of thrust, approximately with a 2:1 ratio. Operating in monopropellant mode contributes to a specific impulse loss that is dependent on the duty cycle. Again, this has been taken into account calculating the equivalent specific impulse.

Fuel valve timing has been estimated to be 50 ms, sufficient to provide the required accuracy for the attitude control system.

The attitude control penalty calculations have determined that the four engines solution provides a higher equivalent specific impulse than the single engine one. For the detailed analyses the reader is referred to [37].

Due to this result and the other reasons previously mentioned the single engine option has been discarded.

Fig. 26. Open view of the propulsion-recovery module

The four thrusters are divided in 4 complete independent propulsion units for market purposes and industrialization (see Fig. 26). Each propulsion unit has its own electronic control board to guarantee a plug-and-play feature. Moreover, each propulsion unit includes two cold gas thrusters for pulsed reaction roll control (Fig. 25 and 26).

6. Further considerations

Once the EARS architecture has been defined and the subsystems have been preliminary sized, it is possible to check the final global results.

The propulsion and recovery module has a height of 250 mm. The original bus has a height of 230 mm. The payload bay has a height of 350 mm. The heatshield box has a height around 200 mm plus 80 mm of the fixed nose. So, the total length is around 1.1 m, which is both compatible with the maximum satellite height of the MP42 platform and the stability margin calculated by the analyses in the mission design. However, this slightly exceeds the limits for the Falcon 9 rideshare options, thus a possible reduction of the payload bay (and/or a potential optimization of other parts) could be considered.

A preliminary mass budget analysis has been completed, as shown in Table 4. While packaging in terms of size is not the major concern, fulfil the target objectives for the masses of the various subsystems is a more challenging task. If the weight objectives are not met, the payload capacity could be compromised.

Therefore, the design and development of the bus and subsystems must carefully take into account this aspect. It may be necessary to implement mass reduction strategies like the use of lightweight materials (e.g. composites) or structures (e.g. isogrid). This challenge is further compounded by the requirement to withstand multiple load cycles in a reusable scenario. As anticipated, the original MP42 platform is not intended for this type of mission. Nevertheless, the conservative parameters selected during the mission design phase should not make the life extension overly demanding.

Table 4. EARS spacecraft preliminary mass budget

Component	Mass estimation (kg)
Propulsion	15-20
Recovery	10-15
Heatshield module	15-20
Platform	50-75
Payload	10-20
Total	100-150

Conversely, a few added specific critical situations have been identified. One is the behaviour of the spacecraft in the heatshield wake during ballistic re-

entry. Certain external parts could suffer some damage. The problem is more difficult to face for items that cannot be easily covered by some kind of protection without losing or degrading their functionality (e.g. sensors, antennas or solar cells).

Another risk is the heat soak-back from the heatshield during the long atmospheric parafoil flight. Ejecting the heatshield has an advantage in this regard.

Finally, the last issue is the long gliding flight in the atmosphere. Cold temperatures, humidity and Corona discharges are all possible threats. Theoretically, the heat soak-back could be used to keep warm the satellite in the cold weather, but the actual feasibility is doubtful.

Again, the items most at risk are the ones on the external surfaces as the internal parts can be somehow more easily protected from the external environment. It is possible to think that these external items will have to be refurbished in the first versions of the system. After having analysed the recovered parts, it will be possible to assess the damage and identify possible design improvements for increased reusability.

In the orbital configuration the added modules do not interfere with the original bus capabilities. In fact, antennas, payloads, sensors, solar panels and the like are free to laterally point to the external environment. This is one of the original goals of the EARS project in order to increase the system flexibility and make it possible to apply this technology to standard satellites to make them reusable, on the contrary of dedicated systems like conventional capsules and spaceplanes.

Fig. 27. Possible EARS in-orbit configuration

The more powerful deployable solar panels could potentially be extended in orbit (see Fig. 27), but the main issue is that any large object extending from the spacecraft may interfere with the deployment and operation of the inflatable heatshield. For this reason, any robotic arm, boom, or deployable system must be capable of retracting before re-entry (see Fig. 28). Currently, the existing mechanism for solar panel deployment does not meet this requirement. As a result, the baseline EARS platform will use the less efficient body-mounted configuration. However, an upgraded version could reintroduce the deployable solar panels once a more advanced two-way system, possibly using

small electric actuators, is developed. A possible further advantage of specifically designed extendable solar panels could be that in the closed position the solar cells are pointing inwards while the external sides are covered with some protections.

Fig. 28. EARS re-entry configuration

Anyway, all that being said, at the current status of the project, the data obtained so far favourably confirm the feasibility of the EARS mission and architecture designs.

7. Conclusions

The EARS project aims to design a reusable satellite able to be sent into space and brought back on Earth multiple times. The concept foresees to start from a KNA Small satellite platform, the MP42, and to add an inflatable heatshield on the top side and a recovery-propulsion module on the other side. The satellite will deorbit precisely thanks to a differentially steerable liquid propulsion system and re-enter the atmosphere in a ballistic trajectory after heatshield deployment. The satellite will then be retrieved in mid-air by a helicopter and returned to the support facility for post-flight check. Finally, after refurbishment and re-qualification the system can be intended for another mission cycle.

The system design studies performed so far have proven the effectiveness of the proposed architecture, identifying off-the-shelf solutions for many components and critical but not exotic technologies to be developed. The preliminary sizing for all subsystems has been performed. The results demonstrate the feasibility of the original concept and design solutions, highlighting however some aspects that need careful attention during further developments.

In particular, a special focus should be given on the weight optimization of the whole platform and its subsystems.

Moreover, it is necessary to study the interactions with the external ambient by the platform and its external parts, first behind the heatshield wake during re-entry and afterwards during the long gliding descent in the atmosphere.

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